

Synthesis of Mixed Complexes of Aluminium

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Reactions in 1 : 1 : 1 stoichiometry of $Al(OPr^1)$, with hexylene glycol ($C_6H_{12}O_2$) and the Schiff base have resulted in the synthesis of (SB) $Al(C_6H_{12}O_2)$ type of asymmetrical derivatives (where SB^- is the anion of monofunctional bidentate Schiff base). Similar reactions in 2 : 1 : 2 molar ratios have yielded, (S'B') $Al(C_6H_{12}O_2)_2$ - $Al(S'B')$, and (S'B'') $Al(C_6H_{12}O_2)_2$ - $Al(S'B'')$ type of complexes (where $S'B'^--$ and $S'B''--$ are the anions of bifunctional tridentate and bifunctional tetradentate Schiff bases respectively). Suitable structures based on IR and NMR spectral studies have been indicated for the resulting derivatives,

ALUMINIUM halides, alkyls^{1,2} and alkoxides³ have been used for the synthesis of a wide variety of aluminium derivatives. Mehrotra et al⁴, have prepared some aluminium glycol derivatives whereas Mehrotra et al⁵ and Tandon et al⁶ have reported some Schiff base complexes of aluminium. However, no attempt seems to have been made to prepare mixed ligand derivatives of aluminium and particularly those in which two aluminium atoms are attached with a hexylene glycol unit through oxygen bonds. The results of these investigations with (I), (II) and (III) types of Schiff bases have been discussed in the present paper.

[where $R = -C_2H_5, n-C_3H_7, i-C_3H_7, n-C_4H_9, i-C_4H_9, i-C_4H_9, o-C_6H_4OCH_3, m-C_6H_4OCH_3, p-C_6H_4OCH_3, o-C_6H_4CH_3, m-C_6H_4CH_3, p-C_6H_4CH_3$, and $-C_6H_6, R' = -C_6H_4-, -CH_2CH_2-, -CH_2CH_2CH_2-, -CH_2-CH(CH_3)-$ and $-CH_2-CH(CH_2CH_3)-$ and $n=2$ or 3].

Experimental

All the reaction, were carried out under strictly anhydrous conditions and an apparatus fitted with quickfit interchangeable joints was used. The starting materials were prepared as reported earlier⁷.

Synthesis of Mixed Ligand Aluminium Complexes

(I) (i) Aluminium isopropoxide (1 mole) was dissolved in dry benzene and calculated amount (1 mole) of hexylene glycol was added. No remarkable change was produced. The reaction mixture was refluxed over a fractionating column and the isopropanol liberated during the reaction

was removed azeotropically with benzene. It was then estimated by oxidation with dichromate solution and when two moles of isopropanol were completely removed, one mole of monofunctional bidentate Schiff base was added in the reaction mixture and the contents were again refluxed. The remaining one mole of isopropanol was also removed azeotropically with benzene and then estimated.

(ii) Alternatively, after the completion of reaction (i), the product $(Pr^1O)Al(C_6H_{12}O_2)$ was isolated, dried under reduced pressure and analysed. Then to the dried benzene solution of $(Pr^1O)Al(C_6H_{12}O_2)$ (1 mole), calculated amount (1 mole) of the monofunctional bidentate Schiff base was added. The contents were refluxed and the isopropanol liberated was removed azeotropically from the reaction mixture and estimated.

(II) (i) To the dry benzene solution of aluminium isopropoxide (1 mole), calculated amount (1 mole) of Schiff base of type (II) or (III) was added. The reaction mixture was refluxed over a fractionating column and then two moles of isopropanol liberated during the reaction were collected azeotropically with benzene. The completion of reaction was ascertained by the estimation of isopropanol in the azeotrope. Now half mole of hexylene glycol was added and the contents were refluxed for few hours. The isopropanol liberated during the reaction was collected azeotropically with benzene and estimated.

(ii) Alternatively, when the reaction (i) was completed the product $(OPr^1)Al(S'B')$ or $(OPr^1)Al(S'B'')$ was isolated, dried under reduced pressure and analyzed. Now to the benzene solution of this compound (1 mole), half mole of hexylene glycol was added and the mixture was refluxed. The completion of reaction was confirmed by the complete removal of isopropanol.

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TABLE 1—ANALYSIS AND PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF 1 : 1 : 1 PRODUCTS

Sl. No.	Product** and Characteristics	Analysis%		Mol. Wt.
		Al	N	
		Found (Calcd)	Found (Calcd)	Found (Calcd)
1.	Al(HG)(C ₁₃ H ₁₀ NO), Light yellow foamy solid	7.82 (7.93)	4.14 (4.18)	310 (339)
2.	Al(HG)(C ₁₄ H ₁₃ NO), Light brown foamy solid	7.50 (7.64)	3.81 (3.96)	348 (353)
3.	Al(HG)(C ₁₄ H ₁₃ NO)*, Brown foamy solid	7.58 (7.64)	3.72 (3.96)	330 (353)
4.	Al(HG)(C ₁₄ H ₁₃ NO)*, Reddish brown foamy solid	7.32 (7.64)	3.80 (3.96)	339 (353)
5.	Al(HG)(C ₁₄ H ₁₃ NO ₂)*, Yellow foamy solid	7.15 (7.31)	3.52 (3.97)	347 (369)
6.	Al(HG)(C ₁₄ H ₁₃ NO ₂)*, Light yellow foamy solid	7.21 (7.31)	3.58 (3.79)	350 (369)
7.	Al(HG)(C ₁₃ H ₁₂ NO ₂)*, Yellow foamy solid	7.01 (7.31)	3.61 (3.79)	352 (369)
8.	Al(HG)(C ₉ H ₁₀ NO), Reddish yellow solid	9.15 (9.27)	4.61 (4.81)	280 (291)
9.	Al(HG)(C ₁₀ H ₁₁ NO), Yellow foamy solid	8.69 (8.85)	4.32 (4.59)	300 (305)
10.	Al(HG)(C ₁₀ H ₁₂ NO)*, Light yellow foamy solid	8.76 (8.85)	4.42 (4.59)	304 (305)
11.	Al(HG)(C ₁₁ H ₁₄ NO), Yellow foamy solid	8.25 (8.45)	4.27 (4.38)	310 (319)
12.	Al(HG)(C ₁₁ H ₁₄ NO)*, Yellow foamy solid	8.18 (8.45)	4.27 (4.38)	304 (319)
13.	Al(HG)(C ₁₁ H ₁₄ NO)*, Yellow foamy solid	8.30 (8.45)	4.25 (4.38)	302 (319)

* Has been used to distinguish compounds of the same molecular formula.

** All are soluble in benzene.

HG=C₆H₁₃O₂.

TABLE 2—ANALYSIS AND PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF 2 : 1 : 2 PRODUCTS

Sl. No.	Product*** and Characteristics	Analysis%	
		Al	N
		Found (Calcd.)	Found (Calcd.)
1.	Al ₂ (HG)(C ₁₃ H ₉ NO ₂) ₂ , Orange solid	9.01 (9.08)	4.50 (4.73)
2.	Al ₂ (HG)(C ₉ H ₉ NO ₂) ₂ , Light yellow solid	9.99 (10.88)	5.52 (5.64)
3.	Al ₂ (HG)(C ₁₀ H ₁₁ NO ₂) ₂ , Yellow solid	9.89 (10.30)	5.17 (5.34)
4.	Al ₂ (HG)(C ₁₀ H ₁₁ NO ₂) ₂ *, Yellow solid	10.20 (10.30)	5.19 (5.34)
5.	Al ₂ (HG)(C ₁₁ H ₁₃ NO ₂) ₂ , Yellow solid	9.59 (9.78)	4.90 (5.07)
6.	Al ₂ (HG)(C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂) ₂ , Creamish white solid	7.52 (7.69)	7.82 (7.97)
7.	Al ₂ (HG)(C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂) ₂ , Light yellow solid	7.10 (7.39)	7.59 (7.66)

*** All are insoluble in benzene. HG=C₆H₁₃O₂.

The resulting solid products were finally dried at 50-60°/0.5 mm for 2-3 hours. All these compounds are stable up to 230° and decompose when an attempt was made to distil them under reduced pressure. The details of their analysis and physical properties are recorded in Tables 1 and 2.

Analytical Methods and Physical Measurements

Nitrogen was estimated by the Kjeldahl's method and aluminium as oxinate. Isopropanol was estimated by oxidation with normal K₂Cr₂O₇ solution in 12.5% H₂SO₄ and the molecular weights were determined in boiling benzene in a semimicro ebulliometer (Gallenkamp) using thermistor sensing. Infrared spectra were recorded as nujol mulls by Perkin-Elmer 557 Grating Infrared Spectrophotometer in the range of 4000-400 cm⁻¹ and nuclear magnetic resonance spectra in CDCl₃ by using tetramethylsilane as an internal standard by Perkin-Elmer R-12B Spectrometer.

Results and Discussion

All these compounds are light-coloured foamy solids and highly susceptible towards moisture and this may be due to the tendency of aluminium to

acquire coordination number up to six. Aluminium derivatives of type (IV) are soluble in benzene and decompose when an attempt was made to distil them under reduced pressure. Monoisopropoxy hexylene glycol derivatives⁴ of aluminium show molecular association 5 to 6 through the oxygen of the isopropoxy group, whereas those with monofunctional bidentate Schiff base along with hexylene glycol of type (IV) are found to be monomeric in boiling benzene. Hence aluminium acquires coordination number four in such derivatives.

Compounds of types (V and VI) are almost insoluble in organic solvents and due to which their molecular weights could not be determined. In compounds of type (V), aluminium acquires four coordination number due to the coordination of nitrogen of the Schiff base to aluminium through a dative bond. But in aluminium derivatives (VI), the metal atom appears to be in the pentacoordinated state provided both the nitrogens are coordinated to the central aluminium atom. The coordination of both these two nitrogens has been reported in the earlier publications from these laboratories^{8,9,10} and it has also been supported by the appearance of a single νC=N band in the IR spectra of these derivatives,

[where O O , O N , O N O and O N N O represent the functional groups of hexylene glycol, monofunctional bidentate, bifunctional, tridentate and bifunctional tetradentate schiff bases respectively]

Infrared Spectra

The broad and medium intensity bands in the $3100\text{-}3300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $3400\text{-}3360\text{ cm}^{-1}$ regions may be due to the hydrogen bonded -OH groups of the Schiff bases and hexylene glycol respectively. These totally disappear in the corresponding aluminium derivatives showing chelation through oxygen of the -OH group of ligands. Further, a sharp band in the spectra of the Schiff bases, in the region $\sim 1620\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is due to $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$. In the aluminium derivatives, this band appears at almost the same position in the case of type IV, whereas it is slightly shifted to the higher frequency side¹¹ in other cases.

Several new bands in the region $600\text{-}700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and at ~ 530 and $\sim 440\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the aluminium complexes may be assigned to $\nu\text{Al-O}$ and $\nu\text{Al-N}^{12}$ respectively.

NMR Spectra

Proton magnetic resonance spectra of hexylene glycol, salicylideneaniline, salicylideneisopropylamine and their aluminium derivatives have been recorded in carbon tetrachloride using tetramethylsilane as the internal standard. In the case of the Schiff bases, the signal observed at 12.5δ and in the case of

hexylene glycol at 4.85δ may be assigned to the phenolic and alcoholic protons respectively. It has been observed that these signals completely disappear in the spectra of the corresponding aluminium complexes providing a strong evidence for the desired complexation through the phenolic and alcoholic oxygens.

The proton signals for methylene protons at 8.18δ and 8.3δ shift down field in the spectra of the aluminium complexes showing their deshielding and resulting in the formation of a Al-N bond.

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